

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI TOSHKENT KIMYO XALQARO
UNIVERSITEI**

*Tarix ta’limida raqamli texnologiyalar: xalqaro tajriba va istiqbollar
xalqaro ilmiy - amaliy anjuman maqolalari
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Farzinakhon Abdullayeva

Master of student in Tourism faculty,

Deputy Dean of Tourism department at KIUT

**TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS IN MUSEUMS AS A SOURCE
OF COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE**

Abstract

In an economic environment characterized by permanent and rapid technological evolution, successful organizations are the ones that are able to adapt their processes and activities to change. This article starts from the assumption that museums can use various modern technologies in order to raise their market competitiveness. Technological innovation allows museums to become more attractive and fulfil their functions better while also using their resources more efficiently. The first part of this paper presents a series of technological innovations specific to museums and the way in which these innovations can lead to an increased museum performance. The improvement solutions proposed based on this analysis can prove useful not just for the museums studied, but also for other museums in similar situations. Another, indirect, purpose of this research is to help raise the tourist attractiveness in museums of Tashkent by bettering the competitiveness of cultural places and museums.

Keywords: innovation, technology, museums, competitive advantage, strategy, development, attractiveness

Аннотация

В экономической среде, характеризующейся постоянной и быстрой технологической эволюцией, успешными являются те организации, которые

способны адаптировать свои процессы и деятельность к изменениям. Данная статья исходит из предположения, что музеи могут использовать различные современные технологии для повышения своей конкурентоспособности на рынке. Технологические инновации позволяют музеям стать более привлекательными и лучше выполнять свои функции, а также более эффективно использовать свои ресурсы. В первой части этой статьи представлен ряд технологических инноваций, характерных для музеев, и то, как эти инновации могут привести к повышению эффективности музеев. Решения по улучшению, предложенные на основе этого анализа, могут оказаться полезными не только для исследуемых музеев, но и для других музеев, находящихся в аналогичной ситуации. Другая, косвенная, цель данного исследования – способствовать повышению туристической привлекательности музеев Ташкента за счет повышения конкурентоспособности культурных мест и музеев.

Ключевые слова: инновации, технологии, музеи, конкурентное преимущество, стратегия, развитие, привлекательность.

Annotatsiya

Doimiy va tez texnologik evolyutsiya bilan tavsiflangan iqtisodiy muhitda muvaffaqiyatli tashkilotlar - bu o'z jarayonlari va faoliyatini o'zgarishlarga moslashtira oladigan tashkilotlardir. Ushbu maqola muzeylar orasida bozor raqobatbardoshligini oshirish uchun turli xil zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalanishi mumkin degan taxmindan boshlanadi. Texnologik innovatsiyalar muzeylarning jozibador bo'lishiga va o'z vazifalarini yaxshiroq bajarishiga, shuningdek, resurslaridan samaraliroq foydalanishga imkon beradi. Ushbu maqolaning birinchi qismida muzeylarga xos bo'lgan bir qator texnologik innovatsiyalar va bu yangiliklar muzey samaradorligini oshirishga olib kelishi mumkin bo'lgan usullarni taqdim etilgan. Ushbu tahlil asosida taklif qilingan takomillashtirish yechimlari nafaqat o'rganilayotgan muzeylar uchun, balki shunga o'xshash vaziyatlarda boshqa muzeylar uchun ham foydali bo'lishi mumkin. Ushbu tadqiqotning yana bir bilvosita maqsadi madaniy maskanlarning

raqobatbardoshligini oshirish orqali Toshkent muzeylarining turistik jozibadorligini oshirishga yordam berishdir.

Kalit so'zlar: innovatsiyalar, texnologiya, muzeylar, raqobatdosh ustunlik, strategiya, rivojlanish, jozibadorlik

Introduction

The profound influence of emerging technologies on museums is substantial and can be examined from various perspectives. Existing research has demonstrated that both technological and organizational innovations play a crucial role in enhancing the performance of cultural institutions (Camarero & Garrido, 2012). Leveraging technology enables museums to more effectively curate and manage their collections, create memorable experiences for visitors, and transcend physical constraints through online distribution and communication channels. Moreover, technological advancements afford museums a competitive advantage by offering superior visitor experiences, resulting in an augmented influx of visitors and increased self-generated revenue. Consequently, one of the key motivations driving museum innovation is the endeavor to boost direct income from their patrons to offset the decline in public funding allocations (Camarero & Garrido, 2012).

While innovation strategies in both the private and public sectors share the common goal of expanding clientele or beneficiaries, their impacts diverge somewhat between the two domains. Commercial enterprises innovate with the aim of gaining a competitive edge over rivals, whereas in the museum sector, the objective is to enhance the allure of a museum. It is unlikely, however, that these strategies would lead to a decline in visitors to other museums. Given that a significant number of museums are perceived as insufficiently captivating, a museum employing technological innovations to distinguish itself is likely to attract a larger audience without necessarily diverting visitors from other museums. This phenomenon is driven by the relatively low competitiveness of Romanian museums, which fail to fully tap into the potential market due to a considerable number of individuals who do not visit museums. For instance, in 2014, 70% of Romanians did not visit any heritage site beyond their hometowns (Croitoru et al., 2016).

Conversely, technology poses a potential threat to more traditional museums resistant to change. With the advent of technology, the Internet, and increased access to information and products from distant locations, concerns among museum experts arise that the public might, in the future, favor digital images and virtual experiences over static artworks (Anderson, n.d.).

The dual nature of technology, presenting both advantages and disadvantages, often results in many museums hesitating to embrace technological innovation. Luiza Pop I, Borza A (Luiza et al., 2016) contend that museum's exhibit a reluctance to adopt new technology on a broader scale primarily due to a lack of clear understanding regarding its role in the innovation process. According to these authors, a significant number of museums prefer to maintain their existing low-tech setups, which are perceived to be nearly as captivating but less disruptive, cost-effective, and easier to maintain.

Given these considerations, the initial segment of our study provides a summary of technological innovations applicable to museums. The subsequent research in the second part assesses the extent to which new technologies are implemented by museums in Baia Mare, comparing their practices with international trends. Additionally, the study offers a set of recommendations for the future technological development of these museums, aimed at enhancing their competitiveness. Museums have the capability to use the Internet as a channel for distributing both products and services (Lagrosen, 2003), or as a tool for communication and promotion. For instance, Romanian museums, online distribution is typically offered at no cost, encompassing virtual tours and access to diverse educational and informational resources. In other countries, museums go beyond these offerings by incorporating electronic stores for the sale of various products. An illustrative instance is the Hermitage Museum, which globally retails souvenirs through online platforms (Pop & Borza, 2014).

The Internet also serves as a platform for promoting a museum's mission and events, fostering public attendance and participation in the museum's activities. These initiatives, in turn, contribute to heightened public awareness of cultural

values, community support through volunteering, donations, and the acquisition of grants. Key social media tools that merit consideration include image distribution platforms (e.g., Instagram), podcasts (available on platforms such as SoundCloud, iTunes, or TuneIn), microblogs (Twitter), conventional blogs, social networks (e.g., Facebook, Google Plus), virtual worlds, online interactive exhibits, and video dissemination channels (such as YouTube) (Pop & Borza, 2016).

Methodology. The aim of this study is to assess the usage of new technologies by museums in Tashkent and to pinpoint strategies for enhancing the competitiveness of these museums through technological innovation. The significance of our research lies in the close correlation between the cultural advancement of the city and the progression of its cultural institutions. It is widely recognized that museums constitute key cultural landmarks and significant attractions for tourists. In the present competitive environment, any attempts to enhance the scenery and orchestrate cultural events for tourist attractions is not enough. A solitary drawback, such as unappealing museums in contrast to other cities, can be the determining factor between a thriving tourist community and one that fails to captivate tourist interest. Consequently, we posit that this research has the potential to offer benefits not solely to the museums under examination but to the broader community of Uzbekistan, its residents, and the neighboring regions.

In order to attain our purpose, in the period 22-23 August 2023 we visited the following museums in Tashkent: “State Museum of the Temurids”, “State Museum of the History of Uzbekistan”, “Museum of Applied Arts”. We examined the online visual representations of these museums, encompassing their websites, blogs, and social media accounts on platforms such as Facebook, YouTube, and Instagram. The data collected were systematically compared with the findings outlined in existing literature, the authors' firsthand experiences in visiting other museums, and online information about additional Uzbek museums. Presented below is a condensed summary of the key outcomes of our investigation.

Results and discussions.

Based on our conducted analysis, it was observed that all museums in Tashkent

routinely conduct video projections incorporating diverse educational tools. In addition to these video projections, some museums also employ other technologies to enhance the overall visitor experience. However, in a worldwide level this technology is already became old.

The State Museum of the Temurids in Tashkent features a hall outfitted with LCD screens displaying educational content about the history of Amir Temur and his ancestors. Visitors have the option to listen to accompanying explanations through headphones connected to these screens. Moreover, each room has special QR-code tools that can provide some videos and photos of objects in the museum. At the State Museum of the History of Uzbekistan, inside the exhibition hall, there is a screen on which documentaries about the museum, its exhibits and mining are shown. In front of it there are chairs so visitors feel welcome to watch these materials.

Disappointingly, there is an absence of contemporary technological implementations aimed at enhancing the visitor experience. Regarding the technologies utilized on the internet, we discovered that none of three museums that visited have their own websites. Moreover, none of these four museums sells items through online shops as well. The web pages of museums are also not created and there are no virtual visiting opportunities. When we contrast the conditions observed in the museums of other neighboring countries and the globally adopted technological innovations, it becomes evident that the museum sector exhibits a diverse spectrum of responses to contemporary technological solutions. In Tashkent, certain museums show minimal integration of modern technology, while others employ information-transmission technologies without emphasizing interactivity and engagement with their visitors. Nowadays the number of young specialists in digital spheres is increasing. It suggests that digitalization is real and adaptation of new innovations and technologies real case.

Conclusion

The integration of technological innovations, coupled with effective collaboration among museums, has the potential to offer distinctive experiences to

museum visitors. For instance, a sequential visitation to multiple museums in a predetermined order allows visitors to immerse themselves in diverse historical periods within a single day—spanning the past, present, and future. Moreover, through the alignment of their exhibitions, various museums within the same city can enhance tourists' understanding of the region's culture, values, and characteristics compared to isolated site visits. Consequently, smaller communities, such as Tashkent, can implement innovation strategies in tandem with collaborative efforts to provide tourists with a unique experience distinct from that of larger cities. In this context, museum experts should collaborate to establish connections between their exhibitions and design guided tours for visitors. Additionally, we posit that Tashkent museums could gain a competitive edge by promoting this project on the Internet and offering tourists exclusive online visitation passes.

Hence, it becomes evident that strategies centered around technological innovation positively impact a museum's sustainability. While the economic implementation of such strategies entails initial investments and increased costs, it leads to higher self-generated income by attracting a larger number of visitors. On a social and cultural level, the impact is entirely positive. Scientific information, when presented in an engaging manner, facilitates easier assimilation. Furthermore, new technologies are likely to foster greater community involvement in museum activities. As technological innovation is commonly employed for the interactive transmission of educational content, this strategy can contribute to enhancing a museum's ecological sustainability, particularly when incorporating materials that emphasize environmental protection.

It is important to acknowledge that not all museums can readily employ any form of technology. Science museums, in particular, find it easier to integrate modern technological solutions. In contrast, employing the same technologies in other region museums may disrupt the desired time-reversal experience that visitors seek in such settings. For this reason, museum experts need to leverage their innovativeness to identify optimal solutions for integrating technologies that enhance the visitor experience, rather than adopting technology merely for its own

sake. Начало формы

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